

VISHNU TEMPLE AT SUSARI

By

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Susari is a village located 2 kms. east of Kukshi, a Tehsil headquarters in district Dhar of Madhya Pradesh. It is connected by road with Kukshi, Badavani, Manawar, Dhar, Indore, Rajgarh and Bhopal and can be approached by bus. Susari was an important town during the medieval period and was under the sway of the Paramaras of Malwa who were great patrons of art and literature. The Paramara kings were great devotees of Śiva. However, they also patronised other Brahmanical sects such as Vaishṇavism and Śāktism and also Jainism. However the number of Viṣṇu temples built by Paramaras is smaller than the number of Śiva temples constructed by them. The Chaturbhuja temple at Dhundheri and the Lakshminātha temple at Kukdesvara, the Varāha and Lakshminārāyaṇa temples at Kohala, all in district Mandsaur, are other examples of Viṣṇu temples built by Paramaras of Malwā. Susari has the distinction of having Viṣṇu temple.

The Viṣṇu temple at Susari is located in the heart of the village in the Mahavira chowk locality. It is built of white sandstone masonry and is assignable to eleventh century. It consists on plan of a stellate sanctum, an *antarāla*, a *sabhāmaṇḍapa* and an *ardhamāṇḍapa* (pl. I). It is in a dilapidated condition. Only the *piṭha* and *adhishṭhāna* moulding of the sanctum, a portion of the *jaṅghā* and *Varaṇḍikā* moulding, the sanctum-doorway and the walls and ceiling of *antarāla* have survived. The *sabhāmaṇḍapa* and *ardhamāṇḍapa* have collapsed and their remains are lying at the site. The temple is dedicated to Viṣṇu and faces north. It is a *nirandhāra prāsāda* i.e. without an ambulatory around the sanctum.

PLAN

Sanctum

The sanctum is internally square and each of its sides measures 3 mts. The walls of the sanctum and its ceiling have collapsed and the ruins are lying at the site. The ceiling of the sanctum was decorated with a full-blown lotus. The sanctum is *pañcharatha* on plan and in elevation. It has a starshaped layout and is built by rotating a square around the central axis.

Sanctum-doorway

The sanctum doorway is decorated with seven *śākhās* (pl. II). The first and second *śākhās* are plain. The third *śākhā* is a *rūpastambha* decorated with nine bejewelled bands of diamonds and rosettes and lotus-scrolls. The fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh *śākhās* are also plain. The lintel of the sanctum-doorway shows on the *lalāṭabimba* a niche containing an image of four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* in *ālīṅgana* with his consort Siddhi. His upper right hand holds a *paraśu* while his lower left hand is in *ālīṅgana* with Siddhi. Above this is another niche which contains an image of Lakshmi seated in *padmāsana* on a lotus and flanked on either side by an elephant with upraised trunk and anointing her. Above the *rūpastambha* is placed a projecting *chhādyā* which is carved in the centre with a canopy of lotus-scrolls flanked on either side by a flying *Vidyādhara* couple carrying a garland. The lotus-scrolls form a *chhatra* or canopy above the *lalāṭabimba*. The *Chhādyā* is decorated on the upper portion with three circular medallions of which the central one is flanked on either side by two *kinnara* couples. The portion above this is carved with five projecting niches and six recesses containing images of dancing *apsaras* and seated Vishṇu. These images are from left to right as follows :—

1. A dancing *apsaras* inside a recess.
2. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* inside a niche and carrying *padma*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha*.
3. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *abhaya*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a recess.
4. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *abhaya*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a niche.
5. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *abhaya*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a recess.
6. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *abhaya*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a niche. His head has been chopped off.
7. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *abhaya*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a recess. His head has been chopped off.
8. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *padma*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha*.
9. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *padma*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a recess.

10. Four-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *padma*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* inside a niche.
11. A dancing *apsaras* inside a recess.

Above the central niche is carved an image of two-armed flying Garuḍa with his right hand upraised and his left hand holding a serpent.

The lower portions of the *dvāraśākhās* of the sanctum-doorway are carved with figure sculptures of river goddesses Gaṅgā and Yamunā, *Vaiṣṇava dvārāpālas* and female attendants. The right flank of the sanctum-doorway shows the following sculptures from right to left.

1. Two-armed Yamunā standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kati* and chopped off. Only the head of her mount *kachchhapa* has survived.
2. Female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and *chaurī*. Her breasts have been chopped off.
3. A niche containing an image of four-armed *Vaiṣṇavadvārāpāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a mutilated *chakra* by his surviving upper left hand. His remaining three hands have been chopped off.
4. A female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* inside a recess and carrying lotus-stalk and chopped off.
5. A female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kati* and chopped off.
6. A female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *patra* and lotus stalk.
7. Two-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a purse by his both hands. His right leg has been chopped off. The standing Mount elephant is carved on his left.

The lower portion of the *dvāraśākhās* of the doorway is carved with the following figure sculptures from left to right.

1. Two armed Gaṅgā standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying chopped off and *kaṭi*. The mount crocodile is carved on her right. Her right hand and breasts have been chopped off.
2. A female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga*. Both of her hands have been chopped off.

3. A niche containing an image of four-armed *Vaishṇavadvāra-pāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying chopped *gadā* and *chakra* by his upper right and left hands. His head, both the lower hands and legs, have been chopped off.
4. A female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a garland by her both hands.
5. A female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *chaurī* and *kaṭi*.
6. A female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga*. Her right hand has been chopped off and her left hand is in *kaṭi*.
7. Two-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a purse by his both hands.

The door-sill of the sanctum-doorway is missing. However, the *chandraśilā* in front of the sanctum-doorway is intact. It is carved at either end with a conch. The lower portion of the wall on either side of the doorway is carved with a frieze of diamonds inside panels and images of flying Garuḍa either in *añjalimudrā* or simply in flying posture. The sanctum-doorway measures 2.10mt. high and 78 cms. wide.

Inside the sanctum is lying its ceiling stone-slab carved in the centre with a full-blown lotus and at each of the four corners with a *kīrttimukha*. It is broken into three fragments. It measures 2.05 mt. long, 1.75 mt. broad and 25 cms. thick. There is no image at present inside the sanctum.

Antarāla

The walls of the *antarāla* have each a niche which has been chopped off. Only the pediments of the niches are extant at present. The *antarāla* measures 1.35 mt. long and 2.88 mt. broad. The ceiling of the *antarāla* is of *nābhichchhanda* variety and is decorated with three *nābhichchhandas* each carved with *kola* and *gojatālu* courses (pl. III). The ceiling rests on the walls of the sanctum and two pilasters. The pilaster on the eastern side is missing. The pilaster on the western side showed a base or *kumbhikā* consisting of *khura*, *kumbha*, *kalaśa* and *kapota*. On each face of the *kumbhikā* is carved a niche containing an image. One of these images is that of four-armed flying Garuḍa. Above the base rests the shaft which is decorated with a median band of *chaitya* arches. The upper portion of the pilaster is carved with a band of lotus scrolls. The shaft is surmounted by the capital consisting of *karnikā* and double *padma*.

On the capital is a niche containing an image of four-armed Vaishṇavi seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *gadā* and *chakra* by her upper right and left hands. Both of her lower hands, breasts and legs have been chopped off. The figure of mount Garuḍa, shown below her right folded leg, has also been chopped off. The niche is composed of two circular pilasters and is decorated with a *makaratorāṇa*. The *parikara* is carved with *Vyālas* (pl. IV and Figure 1).

The niche on the capital of eastern pilaster contains an image of a seated four armed female-deity whose head, breasts, *āyudhas* and legs have been chopped off. She probably held a *ghaṭa* by her lower left hand as is evident from the extant portion. Each of the pilasters of the *antarāla* measure 2.30 mt. high including capital.

Above these niches on the top of the pilasters is placed the architrave of the ceiling which is carved with two friezes, one of *gagārakas* and the other of *padmapatras*. The bottom portion of the architrave is carved with a full-blown lotus. The front portion of the architrave is decorated with a frieze of *tamālapatras*.

ELEVATION

Pīṭha mouldings

The *pīṭha* mouldings of the sanctum consist of a plain *bhiṭṭa*, another *bhiṭṭa* decorated with *thakarikās*, *karṇikā*, *jāḍyakumbhā* carved with *thakarikās*, plain *antarpatra*, *karṇikā*, plain *antarpatra* and a plain *paṭṭikā*. The *bhadras* of the *pīṭha* mouldings on the eastern, southern and western sides are carved with a double-arch containing a shrine-motif or *ratnakūṭa*. The height of the *pīṭha* mouldings measures 1.20 mt.

Adhiṣṭhāna mouldings

Above the *pīṭha* mouldings rest the *adhishṭhāna* mouldings which consist of plain *khura*, *kumbha* decorated with a median band of diamonds and rosettes, plain *antarpatra*, *kalaśa*, plain *antarpatra* and *kapota* decorated with *kuḍūs*, on the *bhadras* of the *adhishṭhāna* mouldings on the eastern, southern and western sides is a niche composed of two rectangular pilasters and containing a shrine-motif (*ratnakūṭa*). The niche is surmounted by a small pediment. The height of the *adhishṭhāna* mouldings is 1.63 mt. (pl. V).

Jaṅghā (Wall)

Above the *adhishṭhāna* mouldings rests the *jaṅghā*. The *jaṅghā* portion of the *antarāla* alone has survived, that of the sanctum having

been collapsed. It is evident from the extant portion of the *jañghā* of *antarāla* that it was decorated with pilasters interspersed with *ratnakū-tas* or shrine motifs like Mamlesvara temple at Mandhata. The pilasters are decorated with two bands, one of the *chaitya* arches and the other of *tamālapatras*. The *jañghā* was richly ornamented. The height of the *jañghā* measures 1.35 mt.

Varaṇḍikā mouldings

The *jañghā* is surmounted by the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings which consist of *padma*, *kapota*, *karnīka*, *paṭṭikā karnīka* and *kapota*. The height of the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings is 1.10 mt.

The *varaṇḍikā* mouldings supported the *śikhara* which is now missing. But it is evident from the ruins lying at the site that it was of *bhūmija* style which showed four spines decorated with usual mesh of *chaitya* dormers on the central *rathas* and miniature shrine-models of diminishing heights arranged in horizontal and vertical rows in each of the four quadrants. The *śukanāsikā* or antefix exhibited a sculptured medallion within a conspicuous *chaitya*-dormer at the base of spine on each side which contained a significant aspect of the principal deity Vishṇu enshrined in the sanctum.

The temple was covered with debris and has been recently exposed in 1986-87 by removing the debris by the Department of Archaeology, Government of Madhya Pradesh. The ruins of the temple recovered during the clearance have been stacked at the site. Among the architectural and sculptural fragments of the temple stacked at the site, the following deserve attention :

1. Fragment of the *śikhara* of the temple carved with a mesh of *chaitya* dormers. It measures 65 cms. long, 55 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.
2. The capital of a pillar carved with leaves and crocodiles. It measures 85 cms. long, 55 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.
3. Fragment of the *Nābhichchhanda* ceiling of *sabhāmaṇḍapa*. It is carved with *kola* courses and measures 1.65 mt. long 46 cms. broad and 60 cms. thick.
4. Four fragmentary miniature *śikharas* of the quadrants of the *bhūmija śikhara* of the temple, each carved with a mesh of *chaitya*-dormers.
5. A bracket carved with a flying *bhūta* having the head of a lion. He is four-armed and holds a sword by his lower right

Pl. I : Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, General View from East.

Shankar

Pl. II : Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, Sanctuary-doorway.

Pl. III Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, Ceiling of the antarala.

Pl. IV Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, Vaishnavi inside a niche on the Pilaster of the antarala.

Pl. V Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, Pitha and adhishthana mouldings.

Pl. VI Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, Image of a Devi Kept in the Compound.

Pl. VII Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, A sculptured medallion within a chaitya showing Lord Vishnu seated on a throne, surrounded by attendants, including three female attendants (Sudhanvanis) sheltering him.

Pl. VIII Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, A sculptured medallion showing
Gojendramoksha scene.

Pl. IX Susari, Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, Fragmentary Kakshasana carved with circular medallions containing various scenes including five of the ten incarnations of Vishnu.

/kshatik

Pl. X Susari Dhar (M.P.) Vishnu Temple, A pillar of the temple erected on a platform in the compound of the Higher Secondary School, Susari.

Fig. 1 : Susari, Dhar (M.P.), Vishnu Temple, Vaishnavi inside a niche in the pilaster of the antarala.

hand and a shield by his upper left hand. It measures 72 cms. long and 50 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.

6. An *apsaras* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and chopped off. She wears *karaṇḍamukṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *keyūras*, *valayas* and a *sāri* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels, on her right is carved a frieze of swans. It measures 70 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 25 cms. thick.
7. An image of eight-armed Devī seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *Varadāksha*, *vajra*, *bāṇa*, *padma* and *padma*. Her remaining three left hands have been chopped off. She wears *karaṇḍamukṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *pādakaṭakas*, *nūpurās* and a *sāri* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. The mount corpse is seen lying below her left folded leg. It measures 70 cms. high, 55 cms. broad and 35 cms. thick. The image is seen inside a niche composed of two circular pilasters and decorated with a *makaratorāṇa*. The *parikara* of the niche is decorated with *Vyālas* (pl. VI).
8. A sculptured medallion within a *chaitya-dormer* which formed the *śukanāsika* or antefix at the base of the spine of the *śikhara*. It contains a *makaramukha* from which issue out lotus-scrolls. On the right is a niche composed of two rectangular pilasters and containing an image of a female standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and lotus-stalk. She stands on a lotus-bracket flanked on either side by a flower bouquet. She is flanked on either side by a female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying lotus-stalk and *kaṭi*. It measures 85 cms. high, 1.40 mt. broad and 35 cm. thick (pl. VII).
9. Another sculptured medallion within a *chaitya-dormer* which formed the *śukanāsa* at the base of the spine of the *śikhara*. It is decorated with two strings of mangoes on the border. The medallion is decorated all round with spiral lotus-scrolls containing a male playing on flute, monkey and crocodile, flying *bhūta*, an ascetic teacher seated with his disciple, *maithuna* and a duel fight or *dvandvayuddha*.

The circular medallion contains a *Gajendra-moksha* scene showing ten-armed Vishṇu seated in *lalitāsana* on mount *Garuḍa*. His head and hands have been chopped off. He is flanked on either side by a female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and lotus-stalk. Below the left folded leg of Vishṇu is shown the elephant with

his wife and child elephant. It is a unique representation of Gajendra-moksha. It measures 95 cms. high, 2.15 mt. broad and 35 cms. thick (pl. VIII).

10. Fragment of the *nābhichchanda* ceiling carved with a *kīrtti-mukha* and *kola* and *gajatālu* courses. It measures 75 cms. high, 75 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.
11. *Kalaśa* of the temple. It has a socket in the centre.
12. Fragment of a *kakshāsana* of the temple. It is carved with four circular medallions and four shrine-motifs interspersed by two elephant-heads. It measures 50 cms. high, 1.32 mt. broad and 30 cms. thick.
13. Fragment of the miniature *śikhara* of the *bhūmija* temple. It has seven *rathas* and measures 40 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 52 cms. thick.
14. Stone-slab of the *nābhichchanda* ceiling carved with *kola* and *gajatālu* courses. It measures 54 cms. long, 60 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.
15. Fragmentary *kakshāsana* carved with three circular medallions. The first medallion contains a marching elephant, standing female, a tree and horse. The second medallion contains a *mithuna* scene. The third medallion contains standing figures of Paraśurāma holding *paraśu* and *muṇḍa*, Vāmana holding an umbrella, Rāma holding bow and arrow, Krishna holding *gādā* and Buddha carrying *abhaya* and folios. Below the medallions is a frieze of lotus-scrolls and another frieze of four shrine-motifs interspersed by two elephant-heads. It measures 70 cms. high, 1.45 mt. broad and 35 cms. thick (pl. IX).
16. A fragmentary pilaster carved with two bands, of which the lower one consists of *chalya*-arches and the upper one is made of *kīrttimukhas*. It measures 1 mt. high, 43 cms. broad and 20 cms. thick,
17. Base of a pillar consisting of *khura*, *kumbha*, *kalaśa* and *kapota* and carved with a niche containing an image of a seated deity on each of the four faces.
18. A ceiling stone-slab carved in the centre with a full-blown lotus. It shows on the right a panel containing five standing images of two-armed male-deities, on the left is seen another

panel containing four images of two-armed male-deities of which three are standing and one is seated. Each of the three compartments of the ceiling-slab is decorated on the four corners with a *kīrttimukha*. These images represent probably *Navagrahas*. It measures 1.55 mt. long, 1.55 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.

19. Shaft of a pilaster carved in the lower square portion with three niches each containing a standing dwarf. The upper portion is circular and has a bracket for keeping a lamp. The top of the pilaster has been chopped off. It measures 1.80 mt. high, 70 cms. long and 55 cms. broad.
20. A bracket carved with two flying *bhūtas*. The heads and legs of both of them have been chopped off. It measures 1.30 mt. long, 55 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.
21. A bracket carved with two flying *bhūtas*. The head of one *bhūta*, who holds an arrow by his both hands, has been chopped off. It measures 90 cms. long, 90 cms. broad and 35 cms. thick.
22. A bracket carved with five flying *bhūtas*. It measures 1.40 mt. long, 1.40 mt. broad and 35 cms. thick.
23. An amorous couple inside a niche. The head of the male and right leg of the female have been chopped off. They are seen kissing each other. It measures 58 cms. high, 35 cms. broad and 30 cms. thick.
24. A stone-lintel of the doorway carved with five niche-shrines and four recesses. Each niche-shrine contains an image of a two-armed *Devī* seated in *lalitāsana* and holding chopped *āyudhas*, while each recess shows a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga*. The *śikharas* of the niche-shrines are interspersed with two seated elephants and two lions. It measures 1.60 mt. long, 55 cms high and 30 cms. thick.
25. A bracket carved with a *bhūta* couple i.e. a male and a female *bhūtas* in *ālīṅgana*. It measures 80 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 32 cms. thick. It is a rare piece.
26. The lower portion of an image, a deity seated in *lalitāsana* on a full-blown lotus. Only the right hand of the image in chopped form is extant. The portion of the image above the waist has been chopped off. It measures 28 cms. high, 35 cms. broad and 18 cms. thick.

27. Fragment of *kakshāsana* carved with a circular medallion containing a dancing male, a dwarf male attendant, a female and a flying figure probably a *Vidyādhara*. It measures 32 cms high, 40 cms. broad and 10 cms. thick.
28. Bracket carved with five flying *bhūtas*. One of the *bhūtas* carries a chopped *hāra*, while the other *bhūta* is seen playing on a drum. The figures of the remaining three *bhūtas* have been chopped off. It measures 1.40 mt. long, 1.40 mt. broad and 35 cms. thick.

Besides, fragments of sculptured medallions within *chaitya* dormers which decorated the bases of the spines of the *śikhara*, a *kīrttimukha* and capitals of pillars are also lying at the site.

The temple is at present under the protection of the Department of Archaeology, Government of Madhya Pradesh.

There are a number of mason marks on the temple in characters of eleventh century A.D. which read as 'Amadeva' and 'Visala'. These are the names of the architects who worked at the site and built the temple.

Some of the architectural and sculptural members of the temple have been shifted to the Higher Secondary School, Susari and are kept in the compound.

On a platform under a banyan tree is erected a pillar of the Vishnu temple. The base or *kumbhikā* of the pillar is square and plain. The shaft is also square in the lower portion where it is carved with a niche on each of the four faces. Each of these niches contains an image of a four-armed Devi standing in *tribhaṅga* and wearing *jaṭāmukuṭa*. The upper portion of the shaft is circular where it is carved with lotus-scrolls. This portion of the shaft is decorated with two octagonal bands, one of the *kīrttimukhas* from which bells are seen hanging and the other of *chaitya*-arches. It measures 2.40 mt. high, 70 cms. long and 70 cms. broad. The pillar probably belonged to the *sabhāmaṇḍapa* of the temple. (pl. X).

2. An image of four-armed *Vaiṣṇava-dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *padma* and *gadā* in his lower hands. Both of his upper hands have been chopped off. He wears *kirīṭamukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *yajñopavīta*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *pādakaṭakas*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a

mekhalā with loops and tassels and a scarf. His head, left leg and both the feet have been chopped off. He is flanked on either side by a two-armed male-deity seated in *lalitāsana*. The hands of the male-deity have been chopped off. The head of *Vaishṇava-dvārapāla* is flanked on either side by a flying *Vidyādhara* carrying a garland. It measures 1.30 mt. high, 45^ocms. broad and 40 cms. thick.

3. Fragment of *kakshāsana* carved with two circular medallions and a niche, one of the medallions contains a couple blowing conch. The other medallion displays a seated bearded ascetic behind whom is seen a female. In front of him is seen a female seated on an animal. The niche contains an image of a female-deity, standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying lotus-stalk and *kaṭi*. It measures 75 cms. high, 92 cms. broad and 30 cms, thick.
4. Bracket carved with foliage. It measures 1.10 mt. long, 75 cms. broad and 45 cms. high.

Inside the village, on the platform of *Gopālamandira* are kept the following sculptures which also belong to the Vishṇu temple.

1. Bust of four-armed *Garuḍa*. All of his hands have been chopped off. He wears *Karaṇḍamukuta*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, and *keyūra*. The wings of *Garuḍa* are outstretched and have been beautifully carved. It measures 60 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 25 cms. thick. There is a canopy of serpent-hoods behind his head.
2. Lower portion of an image of a female deity seated in *lalitāsana* on a *pīṭha* and carrying *varadāksha* by her only surviving right hand. It measures 20 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 25 cms. thick. She wears *pādakaṭaka* and *nūparas*.
3. Fragment of *kakshāsana* carved with a circular medallion containing an image of a bearded male teacher holding a folio by his left hand. In front of him is a seated female disciple in *añjalimudrā*. It measures 41 cms. high, 40 cms. broad and 10 cms. thick.
4. An elephant holding a lotus stalk by his trunk. He wears a *karaṇḍamukuta*. It measures 35 cms. high, 30 cms. broad and 20 cms. thick.

27. Fragment of *kakshāsana* carved with a circular medallion containing a dancing male, a dwarf male attendant, a female and a flying figure probably a *Vidyādhara*. It measures 32 cms high, 40 cms. broad and 10 cms. thick.
28. Bracket carved with five flying *bhūtas*. One of the *bhūtas* carries a chopped *hāra*, while the other *bhūta* is seen playing on a drum. The figures of the remaining three *bhūtas* have been chopped off. It measures 1.40 mt. long, 1.40 mt. broad and 35 cms. thick.

Besides, fragments of sculptured medallions within *chaitya* dormers which decorated the bases of the spines of the *śikhara*, a *kīrttimukha* and capitals of pillars are also lying at the site.

The temple is at present under the protection of the Department of Archaeology, Government of Madhya Pradesh.

There are a number of mason marks on the temple in characters of eleventh century A.D. which read as 'Amadeva' and 'Visala'. These are the names of the architects who worked at the site and built the temple.

Some of the architectural and sculptural members of the temple have been shifted to the Higher Secondary School, Susari and are kept in the compound.

On a platform under a banyan tree is erected a pillar of the Vishnu temple. The base or *kumbhikā* of the pillar is square and plain. The shaft is also square in the lower portion where it is carved with a niche on each of the four faces. Each of these niches contains an image of a four-armed *Devī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and wearing *jaṭāmukūṭa*. The upper portion of the shaft is circular where it is carved with lotus-scrolls. This portion of the shaft is decorated with two octagonal bands, one of the *kīrttimukhas* from which bells are seen hanging and the other of *chaitya*-arches. It measures 2.40 mt. high, 70 cms. long and 70 cms. broad. The pillar probably belonged to the *sabhāmaṇḍapa* of the temple. (pl. X).

2. An image of four-armed *Vaiṣṇava-dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *padma* and *gadā* in his lower hands. Both of his upper hands have been chopped off. He wears *kīṛṭamukūṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *yajñopavīta*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *pādakaṭakas*, a long *mālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by a

mekhalā with loops and tassels and a scarf. His head, left leg and both the feet have been chopped off. He is flanked on either side by a two-armed male-deity seated in *lalitāsana*. The hands of the male-deity have been chopped off. The head of *Vaishṇava-dvārapāla* is flanked on either side by a flying *Vidyādhara* carrying a garland. It measures 1.30 mt. high, 45²cms. broad and 40 cms. thick.

3. Fragment of *kakshāsana* carved with two circular medallions and a niche, one of the medallions contains a couple blowing conch. The other medallion displays a seated bearded ascetic behind whom is seen a female. In front of him is seen a female seated on an animal. The niche contains an image of a female-deity, standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying lotus-stalk and *kaṭi*. It measures 75 cms. high, 92 cms. broad and 30 cms, thick.
4. Bracket carved with foliage. It measures 1.10 mt. long, 75 cms. broad and 45 cms. high.

Inside the village, on the platform of Gopālamandira are kept the following sculptures which also belong to the Vishṇu temple.

1. Bust of four-armed Garuḍa. All of his hands have been chopped off. He wears *Karaṇḍamukuta*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, and *keyūra*. The wings of Garuḍa are outstretched and have been beautifully carved. It measures 60 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 25 cms. thick. There is a canopy of serpent-hoods behind his head.
2. Lower portion of an image of a female deity seated in *lalitāsana* on a *pīṭha* and carrying *varadāksha* by her only surviving right hand. It measures 20 cms. high, 50 cms. broad and 25 cms. thick. She wears *pādakaṭaka* and *nūparas*.
3. Fragment of *kakshāsana* carved with a circular medallion containing an image of a bearded male teacher holding a folio by his left hand. In front of him is a seated female disciple in *aṅjalimudrā*. It measures 41 cms. high, 40 cms. broad and 10 cms. thick.
4. An elephant holding a lotus stalk by his trunk. He wears a *karaṇḍamukuta*. It measures 35 cms. high, 30 cms. broad and 20 cms. thick.

In the Naya Mohalla locality of Susari are lying two fragmentary pillars which probably belong to Vishnu temple. Each of them has a shaft, square in the lower portion, sixteen-sided in the middle portion and circular at the top where it is decorated with a plain band. The top of the shaft is carved with leaf-motif. One of the pillars measures 1.60 mt. high, 35 cms. long and 35 cms. broad. The other pillar measures 1.37 mt. high, 35 cms. long and 35 cms. broad.

It may be concluded here that Susari was an important town of Malwa during the reign of Paramaras in eleventh century A.D. The Vishnu temple here is an important landmark among the Vaishnava temples of Paramaras. The temple is remarkable for its stellate plan and sculptures including Gajendramoksha.

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